

Table 1. Reaction* of some susceptible and resistant check varieties to 7 BPH populations in the Mekong Delta, Tiengiang, Vietnam, 1991.

Variety	Gene for resistance	BPH population													
		Chau Thanh, Tiengiang		Longho, Cuulong		Chauthanh, Bentre		Caolan, Dongthap		Thoaison, Angiang		Gionggieng, Kiengiang		Baclieu, Minhhai	
		Score ^b	Reaction	Score	Reaction	Score	Reaction	Score	Reaction	Score	Reaction	Score	Reaction	Score	Reaction
TN1	None	9.0	S	9.0	S	9.0	S	9.0	S	9.0	S	9.0	S	9.0	S
Mudgo	<i>Bph 1</i>	7.6	S	5.6	S	7.6	S	7.6	S	7.0	S	7.6	S	7.6	S
ASD7	<i>bph 2</i>	7.6	S	7.6	S	8.3	S	7.0	S	7.0	S	8.3	S	8.3	S
Rathu Heenati	<i>Bph 3</i>	1.0	R	1.0	R	1.0	R	1.0	R	1.0	R	1.0	R	1.0	R
Babawee	<i>bph 4</i>	5.6	S	5.0	MS	6.3	S	5.6	S	5.0	MS	7.0	S	6.3	S
Ptb 33	<i>bph2, Bph 3</i>	1.0	R	1.0	R	1.0	R	1.0	R	1.0	R	1.0	R	1.0	R

*R = resistant, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible. ^bScore = av of 3 replications.

Table 2. Reaction* of some susceptible and resistant check varieties to BPH biotypes in Asia and the Mekong Delta, Vietnam.

Variety	Gene for resistance	IRRI, Philippines ^b			Bangladesh ^b	Sri Lanka ^b	India ^b		Mekong Delta, Vietnam ^c
		Biotype 1	Biotype 2	Biotype 3			Hyderabad	Cuttack	
TN1	None	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
Mudgo	<i>Bph 1</i>	R	S	R	S	S	S	S	S
ASD7	<i>bph 2</i>	R	R	S	S	S	S	S	S
Rathu Heenati	<i>Bph 3</i>	R	R	R	R	R	S	S	R
Babawee	<i>bph 4</i>	R	R	R	R	R	R	S	S
Ptb 33	<i>bph 2, Bph 3</i>	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
ARC10550	<i>bph 5</i>	S	S	S	R	R	R	R	-

*R = resistant, S = susceptible. ^bData from O. Mochida and E. A. Heinrichs, 1980. ^cData from N. L. Chau, Nguyen Cong Thuat, and Vu Thi Chai, 1991.

Rice resistance to leafhopper (LF) in tidal wetlands

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We field-tested 22 promising lines for resistance to LF in the tidal wetlands of Tarantang, South Kalimantan, during the 1991-92 wet season.

Seedlings of each line were transplanted 21 d after seeding at 25 × 25-cm spacing in a 20-m² plot with three replications. Recommended agronomic practices were followed. We evaluated LF damage 45 d after transplanting.

Line IR24637-38-2-2 is resistant and other lines are moderately resistant (see table). ■

Reaction of promising lines to LF. Tarantang, South Kalimantan, Indonesia, 1991-92 wet season.

Line	Score ^a	Reaction ^b	Line	Score ^a	Reaction ^b
IR24637-38-2-2	1	R	IR13426-19-2	3	MR
IR21567-9-2-2-3-1-3	3	MR	IR11288-B-B-69-1	3	MR
IR31429-14-2-3	3	MR	B5344-Sm-61-2-1	3	MR
IR31432-7-2	3	MR	B5332-3d-Mr-2-4	3	MR
IR51500-AC9-7	3	MR	B6992d-99-KA-2	3	MR
IR9884-54-3-1E-P1	3	MR	IR33353-64-1-3-1	3	MR
IR15865-430-3-1-3	3	MR	IR36	5	S

^aScored using 0-9 scale of *Standard evaluation system for rice*. ^bR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, S = susceptible.

Reaction of IR varieties to the brown planthopper (BPH) population in Raipur, Madhya Pradesh, India

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Twenty-one IR varieties were tested against a BPH *Nilaparvata lugens*

population in a glasshouse at Raipur in 1991.

Ten-d-old seedlings of those varieties, susceptible check TN1, resistant check PTB33, and ASD7 and Mudgo were infested with 4- to 6-d-old BPH nymphs. We rated the injury of each seedling when more than 90% of the TN1 were dead.

Only IR62 and IR64 are resistant, IR34, IR36, and IR56 are moderately

Reaction of IR varieties to BPH population at Raipur, MP, India, 1991.

Variety	Seedlings tested (no.)	Replications (no.)	Av damage score ^a	Remark ^b
IR8	58	3	8.0	S
IR20	38	2	8.5	S
IR22	37	2	9.0	S
IR24	33	2	9.0	S
IR26	33	2	9.0	S
IR28	31	2	7.6	S
IR30	34	2	5.6	S
IR34	84	5	4.9	MR
IR36	62	4	4.8	MR
IR38	57	3	9.0	S
IR40	77	4	9.0	S
IR42	75	4	9.0	S
IR43	37	2	9.0	S
IR45	70	4	9.0	S
IR46	42	3	7.02	S
IR48	55	3	9.0	S
IR50	57	3	9.0	S
IR52	59	3	8.5	S
IR56	100	6	4.2	MR
IR62	91	5	2.5	R
IR64	19	6	1.8	R
PTB33	83	5	1.7	R
TN1	160	10	9.0	S
ASD7			9.0	S
Mudgo			9.0	S

^aBy the Standard evaluation system for rice. ^bR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, and S = susceptible.

resistant, and 16 other varieties are susceptible to the BPH population at Raipur (see table).

IR36, with the *bph-2* gene derived from CR94-13, is moderately resistant, but ASD7, which also possesses the *bph-2* gene, is highly susceptible to BPH at Raipur; this indicates IR36 may possess several other minor genes that confer resistance to BPH. Corollary to this, IR34 has the *Bph-1* gene derived from TKM6 and is moderately resistant to BPH but

resistant to biotypes 1 and 3 and susceptible to biotype 2 at IRRI. Mudgo (*Bph-1*) is highly susceptible to the Raipur BPH population.

Many of the varieties tested (IR26, IR28, IR30, IR38, IR40, IR42, IR43, IR45, IR46, IR48, IR50, and IR52) are susceptible to the Raipur BPH population, but resistant to biotypes 1 and 2 or 3 at IRRI. We conclude that the Raipur BPH population is different from that at IRRI and attacks a wider array of cultivars. ■

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Resistance of rice varieties and lines to whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) *Sogatella furcifera*

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WBPH has become a serious pest of rice in the Punjab, Pakistan, although it was only a minor pest in early 1980. It begins to attack rice the 3d wk of Sep and causes considerable damage until harvest. The pest attack was severe in 1991 at IRRI's farm and in farmers' fields.

We screened 69 IRRI varieties and lines during 1991 for resistance to WBPH under field conditions. Seedlings were transplanted on 12 Jul into two rows with 20 hills each and replicated three times. Recommended crop management practices were followed. No plant protection cover was provided. Test entries were scored using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (see table).

Results indicate that 31 varieties and lines are resistant, 10 moderately resistant, 9 moderately susceptible, 15 susceptible, and 3 highly susceptible to WBPH (see table). ■

Resistance of rice varieties and lines to WBPH. Punjab, Pakistan, 1991.

Variety or line	Score ^a	Rating ^b
Baggi Mun 122	7	S
Bamla Red 310-6	7	S
BRC16-127-4-1	1	R
BRC16-127-4-2	1	R
BR4-34-13-5	1	R
BR850-9-1-1	1	R
B3906 D-14-ST-16-48-3	1	R
B3906 F-13-13-ST-37	3	MR
CWA762069	1	R
IR13475-7-3-2	1	R
CR94-13	7	S
GH305 (Acc. 66838)	1	R
IR12665-7-1-3-6	1	R
IR13429-150-3-2-1-2	7	S
IR15527-21-2-3	7	S
IR28526-44-1-1	1	R
IR29429-B-3-B-1-4	3	MR
IR31429-14-2-3	7	S
IR31785-58-1-2-3-3	9	HS

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